

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BARRANCO FABRE****FIRST NAME: ADRIAN****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

INITIAL STEPS OF SUCCESS IN ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The attraction and excitement of meeting people and living on a society lies on the communication. Languages around the world, in a formal or informal manner, aim to be the element of expression. For a proper message transmission, certain institutions established standardized grammar rules for the different languages. Oral expression is mostly learned by exposition; nonetheless, written one should always be transmitted by education: ACA-401D coursepack for period one gives the ingredients to better understand grammar standards and maximize students' writing in an academic environment. Certain rules might be considered as the salt and pepper in kitchen, basic spices added if needed depending on the taste. This first period of the first course is the introduction to all resources that we can and must use as EUCLID's students. This overview also includes a detailed explanation of the Turibian style, which is very appreciated by EUCLID. This information is meant to have a common format and structure than can be easy recognized and read, as well as to differentiate the style of a response and a major paper. Moreover, the course includes a video which vividly shows the use of the format and different styles to use in any scenario. After this outline, students must demonstrate their understanding by using it in a first essay.

2) STEP BY STEP

My first task as a PhD (Doctor of Philosophy) student is to create an essay following Euclid University guidelines. A comparison between writing and creating a

cooking recipe is a good exercise that I like to do before any script. This helps me ordering my thoughts into logical steps while writing an essay focusing on the ultimate objective. Always, I have the approach of my grandmother's cooking taste and flavour as main goal when I decide to prepare a plate. I try new recipes and doses given by different cooks around the world on internet to adjust the flavour and reach the objective. Information is easily find as 'a feature of most academic writing is that is draws on the work of other writer and researchers' (EUCLID 2019, 2), and *grandmas* in my case. I learned that trying to mix ingredients and quantities can highly affect the result in a positive or negative way; but the main recipe is simple and flows naturally most of the times. 'Writing down everything you know about a topic is not enough to make a good academic essay'(EUCLID 2019, 1); the order and the clarity of ideas will end-up on a better transmission of the author's own message.

ACA-401 is a perfect and simple guideline to standardize writing in an academic but also in a professional environment. I worked as consultant in UNESCO-IHP (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization - International Hydrological Programme) section and therefore I have the habit of homogenic format in reports. Therefore, I consider this introductory chapter in Euclid's syllabus as a key element for students. One of the ideas that I would like to highlight is part of the tips of Principe 4, and it can be applied in almost anything: 'Starting cuts down on anxiety [,] beats procrastination and gives time to develop your ideas'(EUCLID 2019, 3). My daily routine prevents me of leaving responsibilities lying around with an unclear planning. I consider that my habits apply the FIFO (First-In, First-Out) principle, increasing the opportunity of modifying a draft, a recipe, sports routine or a task for a better satisfaction.

3) MULTICULTURALISM AND MEETINGS

Coming back to the time on UNESCO's headquarters, I remember the diversity and multiculturalism of each section. The different types of English between American, British and Australian were a very small problem compared to the *multi-language* that we mix on meetings and on offices. My former colleagues came from different cultures, countries and backgrounds which made the meetings an animated but peaceful debate. Each point of view, especially the opposite ones, should have to be considered and analyse not just because of respect but for a deeper understanding of the problematic. Evaluating 'differing arguments – explain why one argument is more convincing than another and how they relate to the conclusion' (EUCLID 2019, 2) that must be understood by everyone if not accepted.

After every conference or council, the first draft of resolutions was handed in. That draft was made of the collection of arguments that the different members or delegated shared and justified, hence it contained the citations. Delving into the topic and the drafts of every reunion, I could easily link the transformations and the alliances between each participant, which could be entirely influenced by the political situation of their country. However, in these circumstances I could not consider that an idea or an argument was inspired in one given before came from plagiarism because the explanation that came afterwards. Council members argumentation 'must look very different than

how the other member 'originally' said it (EUCLID 2019, 8), and in most of the cases they cited the source of their ideas.

4) THE AUTHOR'S EYE

In general, I like to be surrounded by a multicultural environment in which we taste different types of food but moreover, in which anything can happen suddenly. Sometimes is difficult to understand the beliefs or opinions of my group of friends, but even if I do not agree with them I respect their view. 'One strategy for taking a view seriously is to "argue against yourself" when you make a criticism' (EUCLID 2019, 15) and that would help you value and appreciate the diversity of thinking. Regarding this course manual and by using the Turabian guidelines, the difference between paraphrasing and quoting is quite clear; including how and when I should highlight key words to help transmit my message (EUCLID 2019, 9–13).

The grammatical rules and suggestions given in this manual result quite handy in certain situations, for example when I must 'use parallel construction to make a strong point and create a smooth flow' (EUCLID 2019, 17) and avoiding ambiguity. I did not remember some basic rules as the place of punctuation in the British English writing, hence this the standardisation of essays for Euclid University is well prepared and easy explained. Somethings are easier in theory than in practice. For example, my sister lives in London and she comes to visit once a year with her husband Siar. She always takes pleasure in watching my confusion while I am talking with Siar, because he has a strong British accent. Vocabulary can be learned easily but the pronunciation and intonation in listening comprehension will be master by practicing it. This demonstrates that either for oral or for written communication, a basis practice is required for improvement.

5) CONCLUSION

Writing is always a challenge for me, because being sited and staying focus on a white paper is not one of my bigger abilities but it is the one I would like to develop. Writing a formal document demonstrates not only a master of the language and of the subject but values such as patience, perseverance and commitment. ACA-401D coursepack is a complete guideline about the norms and forms every EUCLID student must master to flourish in every step of the programme. The collect of the subject boarded such citations, plagiarism, grammatical rules, style and so forth, is the least that I will expect for my development as Doctor in Sustainable Development and Diplomacy (DSDD). Combining the contents of the first period manual with creativity and commitment will be my best tool for success on this programme. Considering the aforementioned elements, including the Turibian style, coupled with a strict planning and conviction will result in a perfect tool during PhD courses. All these ingredients at the end will be the perfect mixture to hand-in some delightful result.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central Africa Republic: Euclid University.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.